

ABSTRACT

Does Dysbiosis in Gut Microbiota During Infancy Contribute to Psychological Disorders in Adult Life?

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The human adult gastrointestinal tract is a complex and diverse ecosystem that harbors a multitude of commensal microorganisms, distributed among more than 1,000 different species. The gut microbiota plays an important role in an individual's immunological, metabolic, and neurological systems, among others. The nervous system and gastrointestinal tract communicate through a bidirectional network of signaling pathways called the gut-brain axis (GBA). In the last several years it has also become evident that gut bacteria can affect the physiology and inflammation of the central nervous system (CNS). However, some conditions can cause a disruption in the gut microbiome and result in dysbiosis, which can be defined as "a reduction in microbial diversity and a combination of the loss of beneficial bacteria [...] and a rise in pathobionts (symbiotic bacteria that become pathogenic under certain conditions)[...]". Infancy (0 to 3 years) is an important phase subject to multiple factors that modulate the gut microbiota, and dysbiosis during this period may have a link to the development of neuropsychiatric disorders in the long term. Recent research indicates that the growth of neurons is intricately linked to the evolution of gut microbiota. To investigate the correlation between gut microbiota and mental disorders, 15 publicly available 16S rRNA datasets were chosen. These datasets come from 8 studies that determined the intestinal microbiota in infants aged 0 to 3 years that present dysbiosis and 7 in adults (from 18 years of age) with anorexia nervosa and bipolar disorder. We will compare gut microbiota profiles of the datasets using the qiime2 platform. We assume that in each selected dataset there is always a control group and a patient group. Our focus will be on groups of bacteria that can be classified in the following two categories, in terms of statistically significant differential abundance: (1) Increased in patients and (2) Decreased in patients. We plan to look for taxa that are consistently part of one of these two categories in different studies, especially when the taxon recurrence includes at least one infant dataset and at least one adult dataset. We will also check for inconsistencies, which are taxa that appear differentially represented in category (1) in some datasets and in category (2) in other datasets. Preliminary results show that the genus *Clostridium* is in category (1).

Keywords: 16s rRNA; Anorexia Nervosa; Bipolar Disorder; Gut-brain Axis.

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